

Dopant-free Tert-butyl Zn (II) Phthalocyanines: Impact of Substitution on Photo-Physical Properties in Their Role in Perovskite Solar Cells

Mahdi Gassara,^{a†} José Garcés-Garcés,^{b†} Luis Lezama,^c Javier Ortiz,^b Fernando Fernández-Lázaro,^b Samrana Kazim,^{a,d,e} Ángela Sastre-Santos,^{*b} Shahzada Ahmad^{*a,e}

We synthesized molecular hole-transporting materials (HTMs) featuring a zinc phthalocyanine (ZnPc) central core and modulated the non-peripheral position with different numbers of tert-butyl groups. The synthesized molecules were then integrated into the fabrication of perovskite solar cells to evaluate their efficacy. We studied four undoped different ZnPcs with four (ZnPc 1), three (ZnPc 2), two (ZnPc 3), and one (ZnPc 4) tert-butyl group as hole transport material in n-i-p configuration. Among them, ZnPc 1 registered the best power conversion efficiency with 15.50%, an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 932.9 mV, a short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) of 24.26 mA/cm², and a fill factor (FF) of 68.46%. This was followed by ZnPc 2 which achieved a modest 7.98% of performance. The surface microstructure is greatly influenced by the type of molecules and it evolves from compact granular to fibril structure. Furthermore, the devices with ZnPc 1 showed enhanced stability under an ambient atmosphere comparable to Spiro-OMeTAD.

Introduction

Over the past decade, perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have garnered significant attention as a promising alternative to conventional silicon photovoltaics. This interest is driven by their low production costs,^{1,2} notable power conversion efficiencies (PCE) >26%,^{3,4} and the ease of fabrication processes. Despite these advancements, the transition of PSCs from research labs to commercial markets faces several critical challenges.^{5,6} Addressing such issues is essential to enable the production and widespread adoption of PSC technology. Hole-transporting materials (HTMs) are critical components in the PSCs and have a considerable role in improving efficiency and stability.⁷ HTM layers are essential for extracting photogenerated holes and preventing charge recombination by blocking the injection of electrons. This is vital for optimizing the optoelectronic performance and ensuring the long-term stability of PSCs.⁸⁻¹⁰ Spiro-OMeTAD (2,2',7,7'-tetrakis-(*N,N*-dimethoxyphenylamine)9,9'-spirobifluorene) is the most often used HTM in PSCs fabrication. While it gave excellent performance in PSCs above 25%, due to the hole mobility boosted by the use of dopants and additives such as lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI), 4-tert-butylpyridine (*t*-BP) and cobalt complex.^{11,12} LiTFSI is the main component for Spiro-OMeTAD doping for enhanced hole transport mobility, but it also introduces stability challenges for perovskite devices. LiTFSI is highly hygroscopic, and it can absorb moisture from the surrounding environment and Lithium can migrate to perovskite structure. Thus, this water

absorption can adversely affect the performance and long-term stability of perovskite-based devices, making it a critical factor to address in device fabrication and encapsulation strategies. In contrast, tert-butylpyridine (tBP) serves as a co-dopant with a different set of challenges. tBP is known for its volatility over time. This evaporation loss may influence the long-term performance of Spiro-OMeTAD by altering its electronic properties. Handling tBP's volatility is also challenging for maintaining consistent device performance during continuous illumination. The use of dopants leads to several drawbacks due to their hygroscopic nature, which accelerates the degradation of the PSCs. Reports suggest a significant disadvantage related to the stability and sensitivity against moisture and oxygen that compromises the device's stability over time.¹³⁻¹⁶ Additionally, Spiro-OMeTAD is synthesized in costly steps, which may limit its broad use in high-volume solar cell manufacturing. Despite these challenges, ongoing research efforts aim to address the limitations of Spiro-OMeTAD and explore alternative dopant-free HTM that offer improved stability, cost-effectiveness, and performance in PSCs. Such endeavors are critical for advancing the development of efficient and durable photovoltaic technologies.

Phthalocyanines (Pcs), which are structurally similar to porphyrins, exhibit both photo and electrochemical stability.¹⁷ In recent years, various transition metal complexes of phthalocyanines (MPcs) with semiconducting properties in the solid state have been investigated as hole-selective layers in PSCs. Moreover, metal substitution in phthalocyanines with non-peripheral and peripheral substituents plays a critical role in modifying the electrical and optical properties of the metal phthalocyanines HTMs, adjusting the energy level and the solubility in standard solvents for HTM.¹⁷⁻²⁰ Notably, the unsubstituted copper phthalocyanine (CuPc) complex was vacuum-deposited and used as an HTM in PSCs, achieving device PCE ranging from 5.0% to 15.14%,²¹ with negligible hysteresis, and maintaining 85% of its original PCE after being exposed to air with 40% humidity for 240 hrs. In a report dealing with a PCE of 19.61% and 16.43%, for CuPc and ZnPc respectively reported, this difference in the performance was attributed to the higher mobility of the copper comparable to the zinc, and also to the electron contribution by the metal center to the phthalocyanines rings,¹⁹ thus highlighting the advantage to the copper. However, ZnPc offers distinct advantages that make it a valuable alternative. ZnPc exhibits a unique absorption profile that may result in reduced parasitic absorption, potentially enhancing the overall light-harvesting ability of the solar cell. Additionally, ZnPcs energy levels, while slightly different, are still compatible with perovskite, providing effective hole transport.²¹⁻²⁵ While CuPc generally outperforms ZnPc in terms of hole mobility and stability, the optical properties of ZnPc and its cost-effectiveness are compelling reasons to explore its application in PSCs further.^{17,22} Furthermore, researchers have started to study the effect of the substitution in the α (non-peripheral) and/or β (peripheral) positions of phthalocyanine Zn(II) based on their electronic properties. In particular, asymmetric substitutions on Zn

phthalocyanine can significantly enhance solubility and thermal stability, making them promising candidates as HTM. Despite these advantages, asymmetric Zn-phthalocyanine based HTMs have been relatively less studied compared to their symmetric counterparts.^{22,23,26-28} The potential of these asymmetric structures to improve device performance through better solubility and stability remains largely untapped, warranting further investigation into their application in PSCs. Here we synthesized 4 different ZnPcs substituted in the β -position with four (ZnPc 1), three (ZnPc 2), two (ZnPc 3), and one (ZnPc 4) t-butyl groups and uncovered their impact on photo-physical properties, furthermore, we studied their effectiveness in PSCs.

2. Results and Discussions

Synthesis of ZnPcs

The synthesis of ZnPcs 1-4 was carried out by statistical cyclotetramerization of 3-tert-butylphthalonitrile **5** and phthalonitrile **6** and Zn(OAc)₂ using DMAE as solvent and DBN as catalyst under nitrogen atmosphere. In one reaction pot, the four different ZnPcs were isolated after silica gel chromatography. Except for ZnPc-4, the other ZnPcs were obtained as a mixture of regioisomers (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Synthesis of the t-butyl substituted ZnPcs 1-4 used as HTMs in PSCs

To evaluate the influence of the stoichiometry in the yield of each ZnPc, two reactions were carried out varying the number of equivalents of each phthalonitrile, when the reaction is carried out using three mmol of 4-tert-butyl-phthalonitrile **5** vs one of phthalonitrile **6**, the tetrasubstituted phthalocyanine ZnPc-1 is the most favored (yield = 23%). On the other hand, when the reaction is carried out using three mmol of phthalonitrile **6** vs one mmol of 4-tert-butyl-phthalonitrile **5**, ZnPc-4 is the most favored (yield = 19%). Arguably, the unsubstituted ZnPc from phthalonitrile **6** would be the major product in the latter reaction, but due to its low solubility, this phthalocyanine cannot be isolated. The yields of the different ZnPcs are reported in Table 1. Purification of the ZnPcs 1-4 was performed in only one run by automatic chromatography, using a CombiFlash System. The reaction crude was adsorbed on silica and charged over a precolumn filled with silica. Then, the crude was eluted through the column with a mixture of hexane and dioxane as a mobile phase. Figure S1 shows the different ZnPc bands in the column, as well as the TLC of the pure fractions compared to the reaction crude.

¹H-NMR spectra of ZnPcs 1-4 in DMSO-*d*₆ suggest the purity of the compounds showing well-defined aromatic signals between 9.4 and 8.35 ppm attributed to the protons of the benzene rings

and singlets around 1.77-1.79 ppm of the ^tBu groups (Figure 2 and Figures S2-S6). Taking as a reference the hydrogen in ortho to the t-Bu groups centered around 8.35 ppm in each ZnPc that integrates for four, three, two, and one protons respectively from ZnPc-1 to ZnPc-4, we can endorse that the signal appearing at 1.77-1.79 ppm indicates the number of ^tBu groups attached to each phthalocyanine. It can be deduced, the integral of this signal varies from 36 protons that appear as 4 singlets, belonging to four t-Bu groups of ZnPc-1, 27 protons as 4 broad singlets corresponding to three t-Bu groups of ZnPc-2, 18 protons as 3 singlets corresponding to two t-Bu groups of ZnPc-3 and 9 protons as a singlet attributed to ZnPc-4 (Figure S6). High-resolution matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry (HR MALDI-ToF) was performed for each ZnPc (Figures S7-S10).

Table 1. Yield of ZnPcs 1-4 synthesized in different conditions

5/6 ratio (mmol)	ZnPc-1 (Yield %)	ZnPc-2 (Yield %)	ZnPc-3 (Yield %)	ZnPc-4 (Yield %)
3/1	23	18	2.6	2
1/3	0.5	1.5	1.5	19

Figure 2. ¹H-NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 25 °C) of a) ZnPc-1, b) ZnPc-2, c) ZnPc-3, and d) ZnPc-4.

We performed the electrochemical characterization by cyclic voltammetry in dry DMF solvent, and ferrocene as an external standard (Figure S11a). The highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}) was calculated from the equation: $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -4.8 - E_{\text{Ox}}^1$, where E_{Ox}^1 is the first oxidation potential. The lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}) was calculated by adding the electrochemical gap to the E_{HOMO} value (Table 2 and energy level diagram). The synthesized ZnPcs showed similar E_{HOMO} energy values for hole extraction (Figure S11b).

Table 2. Electro-Optical properties of ZnPcs 1-4

Compound	E_{red}^{2-}	E_{red}^{-}	E_{oxi}^{+}	E_{LUMO} (eV)	E_{HOMO} (eV)	E_{gap}^{EQ} (eV)
ZnPc-1	-1.86	-1.37	0.20	-3.42	-5.0	1.57
ZnPc-2	-1.85	-1.36	0.21	-3.44	-5.01	1.57
ZnPc-3	-	-1.34	0.22	-3.46	-5.02	1.56
ZnPc-4	-	-1.34	0.23	-3.46	-5.03	1.57

UV-vis and emission in the $CHCl_3$ solution of ZnPcs 1-4 were relatively similar (Figure S12). UV-vis spectra exhibit two main characteristics of absorption bands, the first between 300-400nm and the second between 550-770nm, centered around 672-674 nm, these transitions are attributed to the B-bands generated by the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and to the broad Q-band generated also by the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition but with a lower energy state, respectively.^{29,30} To assess the impact of the different HTMs on the optical properties of the perovskite layer UV-vis we measured UV-vis in thin film. By comparing this with the solution spectra, a splitting in the Q-band is observed for ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4, these splitting phenomena are attributed to the H-aggregates formation by face-to-face stacking. Moreover, a red-shift is noted from 681 nm to 722 nm, this we suggest due to the formation of J-aggregate related to the edge-to-edge stacking of ZnPc-4 molecules.²⁹⁻³¹ This aggregation is significantly impacted by the substitution of t-butyl groups on the ZnPc molecules. The absorption for FTO/perovskite/HTM thin films (Figure 3b), reveals the contribution of the phthalocyanine to the absorption spectra from 600-750 nm. We noted a similar absorption spectrum except for ZnPc-2 and ZnPc-4 which is represented by a higher absorption in the 600-750 nm region, comparable to perovskite-only film, this contribution could be related to the existence of Q-band transition of ZnPc-HTMs, enhanced by the perovskite/HTM interface.

Figure 3. a) UV-vis absorbance of HTM's thin films, and b) UV-vis-NIR absorbance and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of perovskite and with HTM (ZnPc-1, ZnPc-2, ZnPc-3, and ZnPc-4) thin films.

The steady-state photoluminescence (PL) for perovskite/HTM (Figure 3b) reveals the quenching of the HTM with the perovskite, the lower emission peak intensity attributed to maximum quenching behavior. We observe the lowest peak intensity with ZnPc-2 and ZnPc-1, respectively, pointing towards the effective hole extraction ability for these HTMs, supported by improved quenching comparable to ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4 (Figure S13).

The fabricated PSCs with the different HTMs were adopted to n-i-p planar ITO/c-TiO₂/SnO₂/CsFAMAPbI₃/HTM/Au. Using different ZnPcs as HTM to investigate the photovoltaic performance related to the substitution in the organic moieties. The PSCs were fabricated by solution process with spin-coating technique except the gold electrode by thermal evaporation, and the ZnPC concentration was maintained at 10 mM. The $J-V$ reverse scans are presented (Figure 4b) and, the corresponding photovoltaic parameters are tabulated in Table 3.

Figure 4. a) Adopted PSCs architecture, b) $J-V$ curves of the PSCs with different ZnPc, c) corresponding EQE curves, and d) statistical PCE.**Table 3.** Device parameters for different ZnPc as HTMs.

HTMs	Scan	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mAcm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
ZnPc-1	RS	932.9	24.269	68.46	15.50
	FS	908.5	24.65	67.03	15.01
		930.6±2.3	24.47±0.2	64.11±4.35	14.59±0.9
ZnPc-2	RS	772.6	18.55	55.65	7.98
	FS	701.9	17.45	49.67	6.08
		753.6±19	17.39±1.16	48.01±7.64	6.91±1.07
ZnPc-3	RS	704.8	17.64	50.72	6.31
	FS	595	16.56	37.06	3.65
		661.6±43.2	17.19±0.45	44.04±6.68	5.20±1.11
ZnPc-4	RS	658	12.93	45.18	3.84
	FS	558.8	9.37	35.72	1.87
		481±176	12.62±0.4	34.02±11.2	2.01±1.83
Spiro-OMeTAD	RS	1057.5	25.09	77.41	20.43
	FS	1031.4	24.81	76.20	19.50
		1034±23.4	24.77±0.32	75.09±2.3	19.32±1.1

The reference cells based on Spiro-OMeTAD measured a PCE of 20.43%, and 19.50% for the reverse and forward scan, respectively (Figure 4c). Here, the best photovoltaic performance was registered for ZnPc-1 with a PCE of 15.5% and 15.01% for reverse and forward scans, respectively, with an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 932.9 mV, a short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) of 24.27 mAcm⁻², and a fill factor (FF) of 68.46%.

Statistics for these PV parameters are in Figure S14. While, the rest of the HTM, showed a PCE of less than 10% with 7.98% for ZnPc-2, 6.31% for ZnPc-3, and 3.84% for ZnPc-4 (Figure S15). To note here, devices fabricated with ZnPc-1 showed lower hysteresis as compared to Spiro-OMeTAD, we ascribed this to the absence of LiTFSI and t-BP dopants, which induce hysteresis in PSCs.³²

We measured the external quantum efficiency (EQE) to study the photoresponsivity (Figure 4d). The calculated value of integrated current density is 24.07% and 23.95% for Spiro and ZnPc-1 (Figure S16), respectively. Which are in agreement with the obtained J_{sc} value obtained from the J - V graph. All the ZnPc show a reduction in the EQE intensity, which is further reduced in the 600-800 nm wavelength region due to the strong absorption of the Q-band of ZnPc as HTMs. While the EQE curves of ZnPc-1 show a higher intensity in the EQE between 300-325 nm comparable to the reference PSCs fabricated with Spiro-OMeTAD, this could be attributed to the presence of the B-band transition of ZnPc-1.

Figure 5. Room-temperature EPR spectra registered on a) powder for ZnPc-1, ZnPc-2, ZnPc-3, and ZnPc-4 and b) in toluene for ZnPc-2.

We performed X-band electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) measurements on powdered ZnPc 1-4 samples at room temperature. In all cases, very narrow and isotropic signals (Figure 5a) were observed centered on values of g very close to that of the free electron (2.0023). The number of unpaired spins per mg in each sample (Table 4) was determined by comparing the intensity of its EPR signal with that of a copper sulfate standard. Considering the intensities of the observed signals, it can be deduced that the concentration of unpaired electrons/holes in ZnPc-1 and ZnPc-2 (Figure S17) is much higher than in ZnPc-3 and especially ZnPc-4. This difference is mainly attributed to the t-butyl substitution that modifies the local electronic environment and spin density distribution of the ZnPc molecules.³³⁻³⁵

A fitting of the spectra using a computer simulation program working at the second order of the perturbation theory shows the presence of two contributions in samples ZnPc-1, ZnPc-2, and ZnPc-3 (Table 4). In the case of sample ZnPc-4, the signal is too weak for the fit to be substantial. The presence of two different paramagnetic species was further established by EPR measurements on samples dissolved in toluene. One of the signals presents a hyperfine structure (Figure 5b), which is caused by the interaction of an unpaired electron with three equivalent hydrogen atoms ($g = 2.0043$, $AH=11.2$ Gauss). The other signal has no hyperfine splitting and is similar to the narrowest of the contributions detected in the spectra recorded on solid samples ($g = 2.0024$). It should be noted that this narrow signal, reflecting a very fast magnetic exchange, only predominates in the ZnPc-1 sample, which is also translated into the best device PCE.

Figure 6. Dark J - V curves of the conductivity measurements for ITO/HTM/Ag, b) J - V curves of the hole-only devices measurements on ITO/PEDOT:PSS/HTM/Ag, and c) Conductivity and hole mobility values for all Zn-Pc HTMs

Table 4. Best fit results of the EPR spectra considering the presence of one and two paramagnetic species, respectively.

HTMs	N (spin/mg)	G	ΔH_{pp} (Gauss)	g	ΔH_{pp} (Gauss)	% Int
ZnPc-1	9.6 e ¹⁴	2.0023	3.4	2.0023	3.3	61
				2.0025	6.1	39
ZnPc-2	1.1 e ¹⁵	2.0025	4.9	2.0024	3.7	38
				2.0027	6.5	62
ZnPc-3	3.4 e ¹⁴	2.0026	5.9	2.0024	4.1	46
				2.0026	6.9	54
ZnPc-4	2.9 e ¹³	2.0024	5.1	---	---	---

The charge transport properties of the four different ZnPc were assessed with the conductivity and the hole mobility measurements. The electrical conductivity measurement (σ) was calculated from the I - V graph within the device configuration ITO/HTM/Ag, using the relation ²²:

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{I}{VA}\right)d$$

Where d is the thickness of the HTMs (the average thickness of HTMs is calculated from the cross-section SEM image of the device, Figure S18, and A is the active area of the devices. To evaluate the hole mobility (μ_h) of ZnPc 1-4, space-charge-limited-current (SCLC) measurements were performed using hole-only devices ITO/PEDOT:PSS/HTM/Ag. These measurements involved analyzing the semi-logarithmic J - V curves (Figure 4-b) using the Mott-Gurney equation ³⁶.

$$J = \frac{9\varepsilon_r\varepsilon_0\mu_h V^2}{8L^3}$$

Where ε_r is the relative permittivity (dielectric constant) of the HTM, ε_0 is the permittivity of the free space ($8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Fm}^{-1}$),

μ_h is the hole mobility of the HTM, V is the applied voltage and L is the thickness of the HTM layer, ε_r is the relative permittivity (assumed to be 3 for organic materials), and V is the applied voltage. The obtained values of the conductivity and the hole mobility are summarized in Table S1. Figure 6c shows the conductivity values between 1.94×10^{-6} and $2.82 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S/cm}$, with the maximum value reported for ZnPc-3. Moreover, the same HTM gave the highest value of hole mobility $1.353 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, but it featured the lowest PCE. For the other HTMs ZnPc-1, ZnPc-2, and ZnPc-4 the hole mobility value correlates with the PCE value ZnPc-1 > ZnPc-2 > ZnPc-4. The obtained values of hole mobility and conductivity follow a similar trend of PCE except for ZnPc-3.

Figure 7. Top-surface SEM images of a) ZnPc-1, b) ZnPc-2, c) ZnPc-3, and d) ZnPc-4 on perovskite thin-film.

Figure 8. Nyquist plots of PSCs under the dark condition at a different voltage from 0.5 – 1.1V for a) Spiro-OMeTAD and b) fitted data, c) ZnPc-1 and d) fitted data of ZnPc-1, e) Fitted Nyquist plots for Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc-1 at 1.05V, and f) interfacial charge recombination resistance extracted from Nyquist plots in the dark.

We speculate other plausible reasons and interface interactions related to the *t*-butyl-substituted side in the phthalocyanine or/and the surface morphology of the ZnPc-3The film-forming properties and morphology of the HTM are central to fabricating high-performance PSCs. Moreover, non-covalent interactions between several phthalocyanine molecules generally cause aggregation, resulting in low solubility in most solvents (chlorobenzene, toluene, and dichlorobenzene).^{37,38} In this case we observe a lower solubility with ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4 in chlorobenzene and dichlorobenzene (typical solvents for PSCs fabrication). The underperformance in PCE was noted by ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4 due to their lower solubility and molecular aggregation. This aggregation hinders efficient energy coupling and initiates the recombination points, leading to low PCE in PSCs.¹⁷ To further validate our hypothesis, we performed scanning electron microscopy (SEM) experiments to examine the uniformity and the morphologies of the ZnPc thin film surface. We uncovered that the best performance obtained from ZnPc-1 is attributed to the uniform film morphology on top of the perovskite layer with the absence of any defect or aggregation (Figure 7a). Further, ZnPc-2 (Figure 7b) presents a similar uniformity as ZnPc-1, in this case, the lower PCE could be related to the lower conductivity and hole mobility comparable to ZnPc-1 (the hole mobility of ZnPc-2 is 35.4% lower than ZnPc-1). Contrary to this, ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4 present a non-uniform film coverage on the perovskite (Figure 7c-d) related to the aggregation of the HTM layer due to their low solubility in chlorobenzene. This inhomogeneous surface increases the number of pinholes between the perovskite/HTM interface and induces the non-radiative charge recombination at this

interface. This is the case of ZnPc-3 which produces significantly higher mobility comparable to ZnPc-1, but inhomogeneous films and this might be the principal reason for the low photovoltaic performance. The water contact angle in Figure 7e was measured to be 83.66, 86.61, 68.31, and 73.18° for ZnPc-1, ZnPc-2, ZnPc-3, and ZnPc-4 respectively. We note that ZnPc-1 and ZnPc-2 show the maximum angle comparable to ZnPc-3 and ZnPc-4 which is supported by the homogeneity of the HTM layer and film formation ability (Figure S19). We made scanning probe microscopy (SPM) experiments to evaluate the surface topology of perovskites, and ZnPc-1 deposited on top of perovskite (Figure S20). The perovskite thin-film showed an average root mean surface roughness of 31.78 nm, while the deposition of ZnPc-1, smoothed the surface roughness and reduced the surface roughness to 14.82 nm. The perovskite grains are clearly visible, while in the case of ZnPc-1 coated perovskites, a relatively smoother surface was obtained. Due to the lower thickness of ZnPc-1 as HTM, the grains are evident, while in the case of Spiro-OMeTAD, a fully covered surface layer evolved due to its higher thickness which also gave a lower value for root mean surface roughness.

To gain insights into photo-induced charge recombination in PSCs, we conducted electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements under dark conditions with Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc-1 cells. Figure 8 presents the Nyquist plot at different applied voltages from 500–1100 mV, and it is fitted with different equivalent circuits R_s+R_{rec}/CPE for the reference cell where R_s is the series resistance coming from the external circuit and R_{rec} is the recombination resistance of the PSC, and another different circuit due to the negative capacitance of

ZnPc-1 with $R_1+C_1/(R_2+R_2/L_1/C_2)$. The series resistance R_1 represents the combined resistance contributions from the FTO, gold, and electrical wires. C_2 and R_2 are associated with the high-frequency arc, which corresponds to the geometric capacitance of the perovskite and the bulk recombination resistance. C_3 describes the charge accumulation capacitance at the perovskite/charge selective interface, and along with R_3 , which relates to the interfacial charge transfer resistance, accounts for the low-frequency arc.³⁹⁻⁴¹ At an applied potential of 700 mV, both the Spiro and ZnPc-1 based PSC present similar values (Figure 8f), however at higher potential ZnPc-1 starts to give a higher R_{rec} comparable to the Spiro-OMeTAD, suggesting lower charge recombination and mitigates charge recombination at the perovskite/HTM interface, consistent with the observed reduction in V_{oc} loss in ZnPc-1 based PSC.

During the different applied potentials, we observe the inductive effect with ZnPc-1 with an applied voltage higher than the maximum power point voltage ($V_{app} > 750$ mV) which arises at small or intermediate frequencies in ZnPc-1 based PSC. We suggest that this inductive behavior could be influenced by ionic-induced defects controlled by ionic accumulations at the perovskite/ZnPc-1 interface. The inductive effect may be related to the properties of ZnPc-1 that influence the properties of the perovskite/HTM interface.⁴² We thus speculate a difference in the electronic interaction with the perovskite layer as compared to the Spiro-OMeTAD, it could affect the accumulation of ionic charges at the interface related to ion mobility from the perovskite layer to the HTM. Subsequently, the changes in the chemical environment of the HTM could potentially alter the interface characteristics and, therefore, the occurrence or magnitude of the inductive effect in the PSCs.

We further tracked the operational stability using the continuous maximum power point tracking (MPP) of the unencapsulated PSCs (Spiro-OMeTAD, ZnPc-1, and ZnPc-2) under the atmospheric condition (Relative humidity RH: 50-65% and temperature 310 ± 5 K). Though the PSCs performance starts to decrease after 1 hour of continuous illumination (Figure S21), for both the Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc-2 due to the rapid degradation in ambient conditions on continuous illumination and loses performance after 12h, ZnPc-1 maintains almost 60% of the performance and showed a nearly linear response in the measured window.

3. Experimental

Materials

PbI_2 (99.999%) was ordered from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co TCI. Formamidinium iodide (FAI), methylammonium iodide (MAI), methylammonium chloride (MACl), and Mesoporous dispersion of TiO_2 nanoparticles (30 NRD) was purchased from Greatcell Solar Materials Ltd. Tin(IV) oxide (SnO_2), 15% in H_2O colloidal was purchased from Fisher Scientific. Chlorobenzene (CB, 99%), isopropanol (IPA, 99.9%), anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.8%), and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8%) were purchased from Acros Organics.

All chemicals and solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Merck) and TCI and were used without further purification unless otherwise stated.

NMR spectra were recorded using a BRUKER AVANCE NEO 400 spectrometer. UV-vis spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 365 spectrophotometer. Fluorescence spectra were recorded using a HORIBA scientific SAS spectrophotometer. High-resolution mass spectra were obtained using a Bruker Microflex LRF29 matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization-time of flight (MALDI-TOF) using dithranol as a matrix. Chromatographic separation was carried out with CombiFlash RF200 equipment using a RediSep® Silver 80-gram Flash Column at a flow rate of 60 mL/min and using a diode array UV detector. Cyclic voltammetry was measured in a conventional three-electrode cell using a μ -AUTOLAB type III potentiostat/galvanostat at 298 K over DMF and deaerated sample solution containing 0.10 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) as the supporting electrolyte, platinum as the working electrode, Ag/AgNO₃ (0.01 M in benzonitrile) as the reference electrode, and a platinum wire as the counter electrode. Ferrocene/Ferrocinium redox couple was used as an internal standard for all measurements.

Synthesis of ZnPcs 1-4

Phthalonitrile 5/ Phthalonitrile 6 ratio (3:1): 4-tert-butyl-phthalonitrile **5** (550 mg, 3 mmol), phthalonitrile **6** (127,3 mg, 1 mmol), Zn(OAc)₂ (362 mg, 1.97 mmol) and two drops of DBN were dissolved in 4 mL of DMAE. The reaction mixture was stirred at 110 °C for 16 hours under a nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was cooled at room temperature and centrifuged three times with a mixture of methanol: water 4:1. The resulting blue solid was dried under vacuum and purified by automatic column chromatography (Eluent: 0-15 % gradient of dioxane in hexane) obtaining ZnPc-1 (23 % yield), ZnPc-2 (18 % yield), ZnPc-3 (2.6 % yield) and ZnPc-4 (2 % yield).

Phthalonitrile 5/ Phthalonitrile 6 ratio (1:3): Phthalonitrile **6** (250 mg, 1 mmol), 4-tert-butyl-phthalonitrile **5** (520 mg, 3 mmol), Zn(OAc)₂ (362 mg, 1.97 mmol) and two drops of DBN were dissolved in 4 mL of DMAE. The reaction mixture was stirred at 110 °C for 16 hours under a nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was cooled at room temperature and centrifuged three times with a mixture of methanol: water 4:1. The resulting blue solid was dried under vacuum and purified by automatic column chromatography (Eluent: 0-15 % gradient of dioxane in hexane) obtaining ZnPc-1 (0.5 % yield), ZnPc-2 (1.5 % yield), ZnPc-3 (1.5 % yield) and ZnPc-4 (19 % yield).

ZnPc-1: ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, 25 °C): δ 9.52 – 9.42 (m, 4H, H_{arom}), 9.43 – 9.30 (m, 4H, H_{ArZnPc}), 8.38-8.35 (m, 4H, H_{arom}), 1.78-1.76 (m, 36H, H^t_{Bu}). UV-Vis (DMF): λ_{max}/nm (log ϵ) 348 (4.4), 609 (4.66), 674 (3.3). HR MALDI-ToF (dithranol): *m/z* for C₄₈H₄₈N₈Zn calcd. 800.328 [M⁺], found: 800.389.

ZnPc-2: ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, 25 °C): δ 9.54 – 9.25 (m, 8H, H_{arom}), 8.37-8.35 (m, 3H, H_{arom}), 8.29-8.25 (m, 2H, H_{arom}), 1.81 – 1.75 (m, 27H, H^t_{Bu}). UV-Vis (DMF): λ_{max}/nm (log ϵ) 346 (4.23), 607 (4.60), 673 (2.96). HR MALDI-ToF (dithranol): *m/z* for C₄₄H₄₀N₈Zn calcd. 743.259 [M-H], found 743.236.

ZnPc-3: ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, 25 °C): δ 9.54 – 9.24 (m, 8H, H_{arom}), 8.39 – 8.35 (m, 2H, H_{arom}), 8.27 (dt, *J* = 6.2, 3.6 Hz, 4H,

H_{arom}), 1.80 – 1.77 (m, 18H, H^t_{Bu}). UV-Vis (DMF): $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\log \epsilon$) 343 (4.47), 606 (4.74), 672 (2.97). HR-MALDI-TOF (dithranol): m/z for $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_8\text{Zn}$ calcd. 687.196 $[\text{M-H}]^-$, found 687.149.

ZnPc-4: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$, 25 °C): δ 9.46 – 9.39 (m, 2H, H_{arom}), 9.39 – 9.31 (m, 5H), 9.27 (dd, $J = 8.0, 0.7$ Hz, 1H, H_{arom}), 8.36 (dd, $J = 8.1, 1.7$ Hz, 1H, H_{arom}), 8.29 – 8.20 (m, 6H, H_{arom}), 1.79 (s, 9H, H^t_{Bu}). UV-Vis (DMF): $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\log \epsilon$) 339 (4.46), 605 (4.68), 672 (3.06). HR MALDI-ToF (dithranol): m/z for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_8\text{Zn}$ calcd. 632.140 $[\text{M}^+]$, found 632.137.

Device fabrication

FTO-coated glass substrates (TEC-15) were initially dried using compressed air after washing with Helmanex, Deionised water, acetone, and isopropanol, respectively. Before usage, these substrates underwent a 30-minute UV-ozone treatment. A compact TiO_2 blocking layer was then deposited onto the FTO substrates using spray pyrolysis at 500 °C with a titanium (IV) diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) precursor solution (75% in 2-propanol) diluted in ethanol at a 1/19 ratio. A colloidal SnO_2 solution ($\text{SnO}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O}=1:4$) was spin-coated onto the substrates at 5000 rpm for 30 seconds, followed by annealing at 150 °C for 20 min in air. After, the resulting substrate was transferred to an argon-filled glovebox and annealed at 150 °C for 20 min. The $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{PbI}_3$ solution was spin-coated on top of the SnO_2 layer using an antisolvent-assisted two-step spin-coating process, set at 1000 rpm for 10 seconds and then 6000 rpm for 30 seconds, followed by annealing at 100 °C for 1 hour and 150°C for 10 min to obtain perovskite. Subsequently, a 10 mM solution of each **ZnPC 1-4** as HTM in chlorobenzene was spin-coated onto the perovskite layer at 4000 rpm for 25 seconds at room temperature. For the reference solar cells, Spiro-OMeTAD was prepared by dissolving 72.3mg in 1mL of chlorobenzene followed by LiTFSI Solution (28.5 μL from 520mg/mL in acetonitrile) and t-BP (28.5 μL) doping was spin-coated at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. The solar cell was finished with a gold electrode (~ 75 nm thick) deposited by thermal evaporation under low vacuum conditions (below $4.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Torr) at a rate of less than 1 $\text{\AA}/\text{s}$.

Thin-film characterization and Device Characterization

To record the absorption spectra, we used a Varian Cary 60 UV-vis spectrophotometer. The surface microstructure was assessed with field emission scanning electron microscopy (Hitachi S-4800). Scanning probe microscopy (SPM) topographical images were recorded with the help of Park system NX10, and an AC160TS cantilever was used; the data were processed through Gwyddion software after fitting. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) was performed using a Bruker ELEXSYS E500 spectrometer. Current-density ($J-V$) curves were recorded using a Keithley 2400 source meter and a Newport ORIEL AAA solar simulator under 100 mW cm^{-2} (AM1.5) irradiation. Calibration was performed with an NREL-certified monocrystalline silicon solar cell. The photocurrent was recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV s^{-1} (pre-sweep delay: 10 s) using a 0.09 cm^2 black metal mask as the active area. External quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra were measured using a 150 W Xenon lamp and a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4 m

monochromator. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed using a Biologic SP-300 impedance analyzer in the frequency range of 2 MHz to 1 Hz under an AC signal in a faradaic chamber, with data analysis conducted using EC-Lab software.

4. Conclusions

Four different **ZnPcs 1-4** with one, two, three, and four t-butyl substituents in the non-peripheral position were applied as a hole-selective material in the fabrication of perovskite solar devices. We investigate the influence of the difference in the t-butyl groups on the device performance. The incorporation of the t-butyl group shows a significant role in the changes in the electrical, and magnetic properties, and the solubility of the ZnPc HTM. The concentration of unpaired electrons/holes in ZnPc-1 and ZnPc-2 is much higher and is attributed to the t-butyl substitution that alters the local electronic environment and spin density distribution of the ZnPc. We find that the higher PCE is not only related to the higher electron/hole density and the higher hole mobility but also depends on the solubility and the homogeneity of the HTM layer. In summary, the difference in the t-butyl group shows a significant role in the PSC performance.

Author Contributions

M. G. performed the experiments, fabricated the devices, M.G. and S.K analyzed the data, L.L made EPR characterization. J.G.G and J.O. carried out the synthesis and characterization of all the compounds, F.F, A.S.S. supervised it. M.G prepared the initial draft, S. K., S.A., revised and directed the research. All authors contributed to the draft and prepared the final version.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360]. Support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation INTERACTION {PID2021-129085OB-I00}) is also acknowledged. We want to thank the European Regional Development Fund “A Way to Make Europe” and the Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación/Agencia Estatal de Investigación (PID2020-117855 RB-I00 to Á.S.-S) and the Generalitat Valenciana (CIPROM/2021/059 and MFA/2022/028 to Á. S.-S.) for funding.

References

- [1] P. Čulík, J. Kouřil, A. Přeč, M. Platzer, J. Teplý, V. Veselý, R. Kudrna, L. Haňka, M. Menšík, V. Panáček, *ACS Energy Lett.*, 2022, 7, 3039–3044.
- [2] H. C. Weerasinghe, N. Macadam, J.-E. Kim, L. J. Sutherland, D. Angmo, L. W. T. Ng, A. D. Scully, F. Glenn, R. Chantler, N. L. Chang, M. Dehghanimadvar, L. Shi, A. W. Y. Ho-Baillie, R. Egan, A. S. R. Chesman, M. Gao, J. J. Jasieniak, T. Hasan, D. Vak, *Nat. Commun.*, 2024, 15, 1656.
- [3] H. Zhang, S. Zhang, X. Ji, J. He, H. Guo, S. Wang, W. Wu, W.-H. Zhu, Y. Wu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2024, 136, e202401260.
- [4] J. Zhou, L. Tan, Y. Liu, H. Li, X. Liu, M. Li, S. Wang, Y. Zhang, C. Jiang, R. Hua, W. Tress, S. Meloni, C. Yi, *Joule*, 2024, 8, 1691-1706.
- [5] M. B. Faheem, B. Khan, J. Z. Hashmi, A. Baniya, W. S. Subhani, R. S. Bobba, A. Yildiz, Q. Qiao, *Cell Rep. Phys. Sci.*, 2022, 3.
- [6] L. Duan, D. Walter, N. Chang, J. Bullock, D. Kang, S. P. Phang, K. Weber, T. White, D. Macdonald, K. Catchpole, H. Shen, *Nat. Rev. Mater.*, 2023, 8, 261–281.
- [7] C. Zhang, K. Wei, J. Hu, X. Cai, G. Du, J. Deng, Z. Luo, X. Zhang, Y. Wang, L. Yang, J. Zhang, *Mater. Today*, 67, 518-547, 2023.
- [8] Q. Fu, X. Tang, H. Liu, R. Wang, T. Liu, Z. Wu, H. Y. Woo, T. Zhou, X. Wan, Y. Chen, Y. Liu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2022, 144, 9500–9509.
- [9] J. Petrulevicius, Y. Yang, C. Liu, M. Steponaitis, E. Kamarauskas, M. Daskeviciene, A. S. Bati, T. Malinauskas, V. Jankauskas, K. Rakstys, M. G. Kanatzidis, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2024, 16, 7310–7316
- [10] Q. Jiang and K. Zhu, *Nat. Rev. Mater.*, 2024, 9, 399–419.
- [11] J. H. Lee, T. Ghanem, D. J. P. Sánchez, P. Josse, P. Blanchard, H. Ahn, D. Lungerich, N. G. Park, C. Cabanetos, J. H. Park, *ACS Energy Lett.*, 2023, 8, 3895–3901.
- [12] T. Zhang, F. Wang, H. B. Kim, I. W. Choi, C. Wang, E. Cho, R. Konefal, Y. Puttison, K. Terado, L. Kobera, M. Chen, *Science*, 2022, 377, 495–501.
- [13] A. K. Jena, Y. Numata, M. Ikegami, T. Miyasaka, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2018, 6, 2219–2230..
- [14] G. Tumen-Ulzii, C. Qin, T. Matsushima, M. R. Leyden, U. Balijipalli, D. Klotz, C. Adachi, *Solar RRL*, 2020, 4, 2000305.
- [15] N. A. N. Ouedraogo, G. O. Odunmbaku, B. Guo, S. Chen, X. Lin, T. Shumilova, K. Sun, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2022, 14, 34303–34327.
- [16] H. D. Pham, T. C. J. Yang, S. M. Jain, G. J. Wilson, P. Sonar, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 2020, 10, 1903326..
- [17] D. Molina, J. Follana-Berná, Á. Sastre-Santos, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2023, 11, 7885–7919.
- [18] M. Urbani, G. de la Torre, M. K. Nazeeruddin, T. Torres, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2019, 48, 2738–2766.
- [19] Z. Yu, L. Wang, X. Mu, C. C. Chen, Y. Wu, J. Cao, Y. Tang, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2021, 60, 6294–6299.
- [20] F. Javier Ramos, M. Ince, M. Urbani, A. Abate, M. Grätzel, S. Ahmad, T. Torres and M. K. Nazeeruddin, *Dalton Trans.*, 2015, 44, 10847–10851.
- [21] M. Kam, Y. Zhu, D. Zhang, L. Gu, J. Chen, Z. Fan, *Solar RRL*, 2019, 3, 1900050.
- [22] A. Hernández, N. H. Hemasiri, S. Kazim, J. Ortiz, S. Ahmad, Á. Sastre-Santos, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2023, 11, 8243–8253.
- [23] M. Pegu, D. Molina, M. J. Álvaro-Martins, M. Castillo, L. Ferrer, P. Huang, S. Kazim, Á. Sastre-Santos, S. Ahmad, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2022, 10, 11975–11982.
- [24] C. Li, J. Yin, R. Chen, X. Lv, X. Feng, Y. Wu, J. Cao, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2019, 141, 6345–6351.
- [25] K. Su, W. Chen, Y. Huang, G. Yang, K. G. Brooks, B. Zhang, Y. Feng, M. K. Nazeeruddin, Y. Zhang, *Solar RRL*, 2022, 6, 2100964.
- [26] Q. Hu, E. Rezaee, L. Dong, Q. Dong, H. Shan, Q. Chen, M. Li, S. Cai, L. Wang, Z. X. Xu, *Solar RRL*, 2019, 3, 1900182.
- [27] G. Zanotti, N. Angelini, G. Mattioli, A. M. Paoletti, G. Pennesi, D. Caschera, A. P. Sobolev, L. Beverina, A. M. Calascibetta, A. Sanzone, A. Di Carlo, *ChemPlusChem*, 2020, 85, 2376–2386.
- [28] W. Chen, H. Zhang, J. Sun, R. Ghadari, Z. Zhang, F. Pan, K. Lv, X. Sun, F. Guo, C. Shi, *J. Power Sources*, 2021, 505, 230095.
- [29] P. Batat, M. Bayar, B. Pur, E. Çoker, V. Ahsen, F. Yuksel, A. L. Demirel, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, 18, 15574–15583.
- [30] Y. Qiu, P. Chen, M. Liu, *Langmuir*, 2008, 24, 7200–7207.
- [31] H. Suzuki, K. Kawano, K. Ohta, Y. Shimizu, N. Kobayashi, M. Kimura, *ChemistryOpen*, 2016, 5, 150–156.
- [32] W. Meng, Y. Lei, Y. Xu, L. Han, Z. Ci, Z. Jin, *Solar RRL*, 2022, 12, 2000586.
- [33] M. Brinkmann, P. Turek, J.-J. André, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 1998, 8, 675–685.
- [34] M. J. Cook, I. Chambrier, G. F. White, E. Fourie, J. C. Swarts, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 1136–1144.
- [35] P. Huang, Manju, S. Kazim, L. Lezama, R. Misra, S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2022, 14, 5729-5739.
- [36] J. A. Röhr, D. Moia, S. A. Haque, T. Kirchartz, J. Nelson, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, 2018, 30, 105901.
- [37] A. Ogunsipe, D. Maree, T. Nyokong, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2003, 650, 131–140.
- [38] L. Caliò, J. Follana-Berná, S. Kazim, M. Madsen, H. G. Rubahn, Á. Sastre-Santos, S. Ahmad, *Sustainable Energy Fuels*, 2017, 1, 2071–2077.
- [39] N. Klipfel, J. Xia, P. Čulík, S. Orlandi, M. Cavazzini, N. Shibayama, H. Kanda, C. Igci, W. Li, Y. B. Cheng, V. Jankauskas, *Mater. Today Energy*, 2022, 29, 101110.
- [40] P. Ghahremanirad, O. Almora, S. Suresh, A. A. Drew, T. H. Chowdhury, A. R. Uhl, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 2023, 13, 2204370.
- [41] P. Wang, M. Ulfa, T. Pauporté, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2018, 122, 1973-1981.
- [42] N. Filipoiu, A.T. Preda, D.V. Anghel, R. Patru, R.E. Brophy, M. Kateb, C. Besleaga, A.G. Tomulescu, I. Pintilie, A. Manolescu, G.A. Nemnes, *Phys. Rev. Appl.*, 2022, 18, 064087.